

Protocols and Institutions

Michael Zargham and Ilan Ben-Meir

This paper is a pre-print of a book chapter that explores the relationship between protocols and institutions through the lens of control systems engineering. Cross-referencing concepts from Institutional Economics, Cybernetics, Control Theory, and Market Design, we define institutions mathematically through correspondence to stability (in the sense of Lyapunov), demonstrating that behavior can be enduringly and predictably patterned without resorting to coercive control. Grounded in engineering practice, we emphasize field surveys as prerequisites for formal modeling, avoiding purely theoretical constructs. Aligning our terminology with control engineering's canonical forms enables us to direct readers to a broad suite of practical methods, while highlighting emerging work on institutional design through protocolization. The chapter will appear in *Web3 Blockchain Economic Theory*, edited by Melanie Swan, Soichiro Takagi, and Frank Witte.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15116452](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15116452)

1. Introduction

In recent years, the claim that society's institutions are breaking down has matured from a provocation into a truism. The growing consensus that our institutions are dysfunctional, however, has not yet produced an actionable discourse about *how to fix them* that is commensurate with the complexity of the problem. This deficit is due, at least in part, to the lack of clarity surrounding our understanding of what institutions are, and (therefore) what characterizes their failure. Answering these questions rigorously makes it possible to think about institutions and their failure through the lens of control systems engineering — thus enabling us to apply methods and insights drawn from that discipline to the urgent but achievable work of revitalizing them.

2. Institutions

The natural starting point for our inquiry is the field of “Institutional Economics,” where the academic study of institutions *as such* is concentrated. At the foundation of that ongoing conversation, one finds Douglass North's definition: “Institutions are the rules of the game in a society or, more formally, are the humanly devised constraints that shape human interaction. In consequence, they structure incentives in human exchange, whether political, social, or economic.”¹ In North's telling, “[t]he major role of institutions in a society is to establish a stable (but not necessarily efficient) structure to human action.” Elinor Ostrom sounds a similar note in *Governing the Commons: The Evolution of Institutions for Collective Action*, explaining that “[i]nstitutions' can be defined as the sets of working rules”² that govern interactions within a particular context. “Working rules are those actually used, monitored, and enforced when individuals make choices about the actions they will take,” Ostrom elaborates, explaining that when it comes to institutions, “all rules are nested in another set of rules that define how the first set of rules can be changed.” This “nesting of rules within rules at several levels is similar to the nesting of computer languages at several levels,” she goes on to suggest, and helps institutions to realize their purpose insofar as it reinforces “the stability of mutual expectations among individuals interacting according to a set of rules.” Ostrom and North thus appear to agree: Institutions are the rules that human beings develop in order to provide stable structures for our interactions.

Ostrom seems to have revised her understanding of institutions, how-

ever, during the five-year interval separating the release of *Governing the Commons* and the publication of “A Grammar of Institutions” (co-authored with Sue E.S. Crawford). The latter paper begins with a declaration that it “is based on a view that institutions are enduring regularities of human action in situations structured by rules, norms and shared strategies, as well as by the physical world.”³ Here, “institutions” are no longer the “rules, norms, and shared strategies” that structure the “situations” in which human beings interact; instead, they have become the “enduring regularities of human action” that are *produced by* or *emerge from* the interactions that take place in such situations. In fact, Crawford and Ostrom’s definition of institutions as “enduring regularities of human action in situations structured by rules, norms, and shared strategies, as well as the physical world” involves no fewer than *four* distinct concepts:

- (1) The “rules, norms, and shared strategies” that make up the “humanly constituted elements of institutions.”
- (2) The “physical world” that, along with these “humanly constituted elements,” structures the “situations” in which institutions can be found.
- (3) The “situations” that are “structured by” both the “components of institutions” and the “physical world.”
- (4) The “enduring regularities of human action” that are found “in [such] situations.”

Insofar as Crawford and Ostrom intend for their proposed “Institutional Grammar” to provide “a theoretical structure for analysis of the humanly constituted elements of institutions (i.e. rules, norms, and shared strategies),” it must also be read as explicitly acknowledging a *difference* between these “humanly constituted elements of institutions” (which Crawford and Ostrom also call “the components of institutions”) and the institutions into which they are composed.

Institutional Economics (as a discipline) is still engaged in the work of litigating precisely how these four concepts relate to one another, along with the related task of *assigning each a distinct (and consistent) name*. While North, for example, identifies “[a] crucial distinction [...] between institutions and organizations” corresponding to the separation of “the rules from the players” of a given game, his characterization of “organizations” collapses the conceptual distinction between the loci of activity that Crawford and Ostrom call “situations” and the “physical world” in which various organizational “bodies”¹ concretely interact. Furthermore, Geoffrey M. Hodgson convincingly argues that the imprecision of North’s terminol-

ogy means that “even by North’s own definition, organizations must be regarded as a type of *institution*.”⁴

We thus conclude that it is necessary to look beyond its borders to find clarity about institutions, and terminology that is precise enough to facilitate both their description and their design.

3. Protocols & Purposive Systems

Although his language often appears to coincide with that of Ostrom and North, the understanding of institutions put forth by Stafford Beer in *Designing Freedom* offers tools for untangling the conceptual confusions opened up by the Institutional Economics literature.

As Beer explains, “institutions [...] are not just things, entities we recognize and label. They are instead *dynamic and surviving systems* [...] they consist of related parts, and the relations — the connexions — between those parts [...] in] a particular organization which produces particular outputs.”⁵ The “specific modes of organization” in which these parts and their relations are *realized* are concrete systems — not just *specifications*, but particular *implementations*.

Institutions, Beer notes, “are actually *outputs* of this system. They are what they are because the system is organized in the way that it is, and this organization produces an inescapable kind of behavior.” Translating Beer’s famous acronymic aphorism “POSIWID” (The Purpose of a System is What it Does) to the context at hand, one could say that “the purpose of an organization is the behavior that it *realizes*.”⁶

Beer thus makes clear that the “enduring regularities of human action” that Crawford and Ostrom identify as “institutions” are more precisely understood as *the stable emergent properties* (or the system-level behavior) of the concrete systems that Beer calls *organizations*. These realized systems correspond to both the “physical world” and the *implementations* of any “rules, norms, and shared strategies,” thus overlapping both item (1) and item (2) in Crawford and Ostrom’s definition of “institutions.” The “situations structured by” this physical world (and its interplay with the organization’s existing “rules, norms, and shared strategies”), meanwhile, correspond to such systems’ *states*. While at first glance it may be confusing that “rules, norms, and shared strategies” are represented in both the *organization* and in the *situation*; this simply means we are dealing with a “second-order system.” Second-order dynamical systems have state variables, which represent the way other state variables change.^{7,8} This com-

plexity is necessary to accurately represent the ways that an organization's "rules, norms, and shared strategies" both *influence* and *are influenced by* the actions of its actors, albeit along different temporal horizons.

Beer's work helps us to refine our model by mapping three of the four concepts in Crawford and Ostrom's definition to a (second-order) dynamical system. What remains is to find a suitable term for the "rules, norms, and shared strategies" *themselves*.

3.1. *Protocols*

What do "rules, norms, and shared strategies" have in common *other than* their structural relationship to institutions? The answer is that all three are means of patterning behavior which be grouped together under a single category: they are all types of *protocols*.

Derived from the Greek *protokollon* (from *protos* – "first" – and *kolla* – "glue") the first protocols were cover-sheets attesting to the provenance (and thus the authenticity or validity) of the documents to which they were attached, thereby operating as "an early techno-social system of administration that has functional equivalents from Antiquity up until today."⁹ Eventually, the term expanded to refer to regularizing practices in areas as diverse as the sciences or international diplomacy — sets of common constraints that function to produce interoperability despite difference, "often independent from time and place." In contemporary usage, "protocol" has also taken on a particular technical meaning (albeit one highly consonant with its broader sense): "a cascade of formalized standards or agreements to be implemented as control regimes for flexible material and/or semiotic organization [... that] predictably structures in an often layered, sometimes hierarchical way the behaviors of data and objects [such that they are able] to participate in infrastructural networks."

The close conceptual association that has formed between the concept of "protocols" and digital technology is not accidental; protocols are, essentially, "distributed algorithms"¹⁰ (the title of Nancy A. Lynch's 1996 textbook describing the protocols underlying the then-emerging internet), or *control mechanisms for the flow of information through decentralized systems*. In *Protocol: How Control Exists After Decentralization*, Alexander Galloway thus identifies protocol as "the principle of organization native to computers in distributed networks."¹¹ Galloway connects the contemporary technical meaning of "protocol" to its historical antecedents, explaining that inasmuch as both usages refer to "conventional rules that govern

the set of possible behavior patterns within a heterogeneous system [...] protocol is a technique for achieving voluntary regulation within a contingent environment [...] a distributed management system that allows control to exist within a heterogeneous material milieu.”

If protocols are mechanisms that control the flow of information (or that structure the substrate by way of which information, matter, energy, and thus also action flow), then the field of **control systems engineering** can be understood as a rigorous and formal study of the interplay between the physical world, specified protocols and realized behavior of the assemblage thereof — thus equipping us with the machinery needed to engineer the stabilization of institutions at all scales, from micro-markets to the most vital functions of a healthy society.

3.2. Control Systems Engineering

Design and analysis of control systems is accomplished by representing these assemblages via dynamical systems. In the context of multi-agent systems, control engineering explores how locally-defined and locally-implemented rules interact within dynamic environments to generate emergent behaviors that are both stable and predictable at the system level — in other words, how the protocols that constrain behavior *within* an organization can be composed in order to induce stable properties in the emergent system-level behavior *of* that organization.^{12,13}

Cooperative Control of Multi-Agent Systems, edited by Jeff S. Shamma, provides a detailed look at the methods (which is to say, the protocols and collections of interrelated protocols) that contemporary control systems use to compose complex assemblages where individual agents, operating with access to only local information and retaining autonomy over their decisions, collaboratively produce emergent, higher-level patterns of behavior.¹⁴ These stabilized patterns are not static, but instead represent the system’s capacity to dynamically and continuously solve complex constrained resource allocation problems in changing environments, all without any agent accessing global information.

3.3. Cybernetics

The cybernetics literature extended the (then-contemporary) practices of control systems engineering to assemblages other than human-made systems. As Norbert Wiener explains in the introduction to the volume that christened the field, “[w]e have decided to call the entire field of control

and communication theory, whether in the machine or in the animal, by the name Cybernetics, which we form from the Greek $\chi\upsilon\beta\epsilon\rho\nu\eta\tau\eta\varsigma$ or *steersman*.”¹⁵ In *Designing Freedom*, Beer revises Wiener’s definition, asserting that “[c]ybernetics is the science of effective organization” — or, we might say, of how to organize systems in order to produce specific desired effects. Beer pays particular attention to “the conditions [organizations] must meet in order to remain stable yet adaptive.” These latter properties are what is meant by the second part of Beer’s definition of institutions as “*dynamic and surviving systems*.” In the context of a dynamic system, “survival” is best understood as persistence of function, rather than prevention of demise.

As Beer explains, “[t]he number of possible states of a system is called its *variety*,” and “[i]n order to regulate a system, we have to absorb its variety. If we fail in this, the system becomes unstable” (1974). He proceeds to invoke “the Law of Requisite Variety — named Ashby’s law, after its discoverer,” which asserts that “only variety can absorb variety”; the implication of Ashby’s law, Beer explains, is that “[i]f varieties in a regulatory system are disbalanced, the system cannot attain stability. Assuming that the regulator has the smaller variety, there are only two ways of meeting the demand of Ashby’s Law. One is to attenuate variety in the system, the other is to amplify variety in the regulator.” Beer is careful to note that “these strategies can be mixed” — but in both cases, “[t]he mode of organization adopted for the system is its variety controller.” In other words, the *stability* of a dynamical system depends on that system’s *adaptive capacity*, which is in turn a function of its “mode of organization,” or *the way that its organization is structured*.

Crucially, the characterizations of both Ashby and Beer are implicitly dependent on a “second-order” model, wherein an organization can adapt its own structure.

3.4. *Dynamic Stability*

In control systems engineering, “stability” has a precise technical meaning: it refers to the system’s ability to maintain consistent and predictable behavior in the face of disturbances. Importantly, stability does not necessarily imply returning to a fixed, unchanging state; rather, the equilibrium of a system can itself be a dynamic behavior — such as a pattern of oscillation or a stimulus-response pair — as long as the defining properties of that behavior remain stable over time. For a system to be stable, any deviations

from this dynamic equilibrium must either decay over time (asymptotic stability) or remain within a bounded region where the system continues to exhibit the same characteristic behavior.^a These dynamic equilibria manifest as “enduring regularities” in the system-level behaviors of organizations — which is to say, as **institutions**, “patterns of behavior”⁵ that persist despite variations in individual behavior or shocks from the environment. The “failure” of an institution occurs when this dynamic stability is lost.^b

In Beer’s time, the ability to apply cybernetics to practical problems was limited — both technically and politically. The methods of implementation required access to expensive computational resources and a mandate from centralized authorities. The discipline’s methods reflected these constraints. In recent years, however, significant advances in technology and mathematics have relaxed both the technical and political constraints. Advances in distributed optimization and multi-agent control provide the basis for a political shift towards “ceding control in favor of coordination” (as per Zargham *et al.*, summarizing Swann).^{19,20} The rise of open-source software development (particularly peer-to-peer protocols which constitute large public networks) demonstrates the realizability of a shift from top-down cybernetics toward bottom-up (or at least middle-out) alternatives²¹ — from the *command and control* cybernetics of the 1980s to a technopolitics whose watchwords are *protocolize and govern*.

3.5. Engineered Institutions

The field of Market Design offers a glimpse into the future of emerging institutions constituted by protocols that have been carefully engineered to produce reliable behavior. In his seminal work “The Economist as Engi-

^aThis characterization of stability is also consistent with the work of Robert Axelrod, who studied the emergence and stabilization of equilibria over norms in his seminal work *The Evolution of Cooperation*.¹⁶ Notably, Axelrod’s models placed the norms that agents used to make their decisions within the state of his models, allowing them to change over time via turnover in the agent population. It is also related to stability in population games, as developed extensively by Sandholm in *Population Games and Evolutionary Dynamics*.¹⁷ Population games study strategic interactions in large populations where individual agents have negligible influence but collectively shape system-level behavior.

^bThis perspective aligns closely with the thesis of Acemoglu and Robinson’s *Why Nations Fail*, in which they argue that the long-term success or failure of nations hinges on the inclusiveness and adaptability of their institutions.¹⁸ In this view, the nation itself is the organization, and its “institutions” constitute the protocols that contour its potential system-level behavior. Nations whose institutions co-regulate each other in a stable and productive way succeed (that is, themselves become institutions), whereas nations whose institutions lack stabilizing feedback loops fail.

neer: Game Theory, Experimentation, and Computation as Tools for Design Economics,” Alvin E. Roth discusses how economists can design and implement protocols to create reliable and efficient market behaviors.²² The canonical example is the development of kidney exchange programs, where incompatible patient-donor pairs are matched through carefully engineered algorithms to facilitate life-saving transplants. These protocols ensure that the exchanges are both efficient and fair, maximizing the number of successful transplants while adhering to ethical standards.²³

Another example of an engineered economic system is a platform economy. A platform economy provides software and serves as an intermediary to facilitate exchanges between users. Rochet and Tirole’s research on platform competition in two-sided markets highlights how these platforms are designed to efficiently match supply and demand, often employing sophisticated algorithms to clear transactions.²⁴ While academically, market design focuses on efficiency and fairness, it is important to critically examine these platforms through the lens of Beer’s POSIWID principle: Despite their stated goals, many platform economies appear empirically to optimize for profit extraction, benefiting shareholders while only questionably serving users, and often inducing other negative externalities.²⁵ This observation suggests a need for further scrutiny to ensure that these engineered markets serve the broader public interest.²⁶

4. An Approach to Institutional Engineering

Supplementing the insights of institutional economics with the rigor and precision of control systems engineering gives us the necessary materials to lay out a general yet *practical* approach for institutional engineering; that is, one that can be *applied* by those creating or governing concrete organizations with specific purposes, insofar as these purposes can be understood as desired “patterns of behavior” which must be rendered “stable” (in the control-theoretic sense) through the design, implementation, and governance of protocols. Despite our use of formal methods, we acknowledge the fundamental subjectivity in the act of representation, as well as the inevitable influence such representations have on the systems they represent. Our confidence that methods for control engineering are appropriate for addressing challenges in institutional engineering emanates from the fact that control systems engineers have successfully integrated economic mechanism design methods into cyber-physical systems such as transportation networks and power grids.²⁷

A fundamental challenge in designing systems meant to *pattern* (and thus, to *regulate*) human behavior stems from the need to preserve individual autonomy even as one seeks to stabilize desirable properties in system-level behavior. Inevitably, governance decisions — *i.e.* those which act on an organization’s protocols — create winners and losers; “the questions of central relevance to governance of impersonal organizations are those surrounding disagreement or dispute among members,” as Eric Alston writes in “Governance As Conflict.”²⁸ In “Aligning Decentralized Autonomous Organizations to Precedents in Cybernetics,” Zargham and Nabben adapt the phrase “control surface” to describe the “governance surface” through which decentralized organizations evolve their structures by modifying their protocols — both technically, via smart contract code, and socially, via community covenant documents.²⁹

4.1. *Institution as Dynamical System*

In “A State-Space Modeling Framework for Engineering Blockchain-Enabled Economic Systems,” Zargham *et al.* introduce two key ideas: (1) blockchain networks can be understood as second-order dynamical systems and (2) that Lyapunov-like Value functions can be used to encode and preserve desirable properties within crypto-economic systems.³⁰ In “Foundations of Cryptoeconomic Systems,” Voshmgir and Zargham argue that cryptoeconomic systems are fundamentally a governance technology, and can be approached like cyber-physical systems.²¹ Zargham and Shorish build on this intuition in “Generalized Dynamical Systems: Foundations,” generalizing the state-space framework presented in “A State-Space Modeling Framework for Engineering Blockchain-Enabled Economic Systems” to control systems with non-numerical state-spaces, and relaxing the control conditions by restricting admissible actions rather than specifying a unique control action.³¹

This innovation – replacing the control law with a restriction on admissible actions – provides the basis for engineering institutions through the design of protocols. Figure 1 demonstrates the intuition for reasoning about governance in terms of second-order dynamical systems.

The framing allows us to reason about the systems as a differential inclusion. Let $z = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ x \end{bmatrix}$, then the dynamics $\dot{z} = \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{x} \\ \dot{x} \end{bmatrix}$ are given by

$$\dot{z} \in \{F(z, u) | u \in U_x(z)\}$$

where the set of admissible actions $U_x(z)$ are still state-dependent in the

Fig. 1. Control framework for governance, rules, norms, and actions. The system evolves dynamically through feedback and constraints. For simplicity, *laws of motion* representing the physical world are compressed into the differential topology characterized by $F : Z \times U \rightarrow \partial Z$.

full state z . The resulting system is non-deterministic, but is nonetheless *structured by* the “organization,” and it realizes behavior in the form of a sequence of values u and z . Such a system potentially has many stable properties, despite the variation in time and non-determinism; these stable properties can be described via Lyapunov-like value functions V , as long as those functions can be thought of as loss functions (to borrow a concept from Machine Learning), and the properties they encode are oriented at their zero value. We are then interested in how the protocol regulates the differential of the loss function:

$$\dot{V} \in \nabla V(z)^\top F(z, u), \quad \forall u \in U_{x(z)}$$

and ultimately, we can claim the property represented by the value function or loss function V encodes a stable emergent property only if

$$\sup_{u \in U_{x(z)}} \nabla V(z)^\top F(z, u) \leq 0.$$

That is to say, if even without knowing the individual choices u , the introduction of the protocol into the organization stabilizes the property encoded by V , in the sense of Lyapunov.

4.2. Institutional Dynamics

The intuition is presented in continuous time because the dynamical systems canon is developed for continuous systems. Our work on protocols and institutions, however, is more naturally situated in discrete-event systems for two reasons: (1) the protocols we have studied are implemented

as computer software, which is natively discrete and (2) organizations adapt themselves through discrete changes to their protocols, *i.e.* passing governance proposals and/or merging updated code into production environments. Therefore, for the remainder of this chapter, we will use the discrete-time characterization from “Generalized Dynamical Systems: Foundations.”³¹ Furthermore, while we retain the assumption that our model is second-order — that is, that a state contains within itself the rules, norms and shared strategies that determine actors’ admissible action sets — we will collapse our notation to simply denote that state $x \in X$, with the discrete-event dynamics represented as $f : X \times U \rightarrow X$.

Let an **Organization** be the concrete action-situation, structured by *implemented* protocols and the physical world, in which actors take actions, and the consequences of those actions are realized as changes to that organization’s state. We *represent* the organization as a generalized dynamical system (GDS):

$$x^+ = f(x, u)$$

where $x \in X$ represents the state of the organization $u \in U$ represents the actions taken by actors, and $x^+ \in X$ represents the state of the organization resulting from the actions u . The unconstrained U represents the set of all the *physically possible* actions u , which must be distinguished from the set U_x representing the *admissible* actions in any given state — those that satisfy the organization’s already-implemented norms, rules and shared strategies.^c For such a dynamical system there is realization

$$(x_0, u_0), (x_1, u_1), (x_2, u_2), \dots (x_t, u_t), \dots$$

which may exhibit desirable (or undesirable) patterns of behavior. Some of the patterning is attributable to the structure of the organization (which we have represented as $f(x, u)$), but some of the patterning is attributable to regularities in the choices of u given x , and knowledge or beliefs *about* $f(x, u)$. In control engineering, one asserts a control law $u = g(x)$ with the purpose of achieving a property represented as $V(x_t) \leq \epsilon$. This is accomplished by learning or deriving a model of “the plant” — in our case the “organization” — and then ensuring the control rule satisfies the condition that

$$V(x^+) = V(f(x, g(x))) \leq V(x).$$

^cWhile some systems, such as cryptographically enforced peer-to-peer networks, can strictly enforce their protocols, we do not assume perfect compliance in practice. Rather, we rely on control-theoretic techniques for *bounding the consequences of non-compliance*.

Although our model $f(x, u)$ is surely an imperfect representation, and our control action is imperfectly translated into the world, these representations help us to create the circumstances under which the organization exhibits the property $V(x) \leq \epsilon$. That is to say that each of

$$V(x_0), V(x_1), V(x_2), \dots, V(x_t), \dots$$

satisfy the property $V(x) \leq \epsilon$, and that we expect the property to be satisfied in the foreseeable future.

Let us define an **Institution** to be an enduring regularity in the behavior of an organization. In our framework, the institution is a property $V(x) \leq \epsilon$ for an organization represented by $x^+ = f(x, u)$. We do not wish to “control” the behavior of the actors within the organization, however, so we will not assert a control law $g(x)$ that the actors within that organization are commanded to abide.

But how, then, can we ensure the stability of the property $V(x) \leq \epsilon$. Are we simply at the whim of the actors choices? We are — *unless* we institute a **Protocol**. A protocol is a set of constraints introduced into an organization to induce a desirable property; in other words, it is a state-dependent subset $U_x \subset U$ that offers our property-preserving guarantee

$$\Delta V(x) = V(f(x, u)) - V(x) \leq 0 \quad \forall u \in U_x, \forall x \in X.$$

This expression does not guarantee a reduction in $V(x)$ if we cannot guarantee $u \in U_x$, but it sets us up to write supermartingale and Lyapunov drift-based stability proofs if we can bound the nature, frequency, and/or magnitude of violations of the protocols within a particular organization being modeled. Control theory gives us the necessary equipment to achieve stability of the desired properties in the concrete system *because* it recognizes that there is never a perfect correspondence between a model’s abstractions and the realized behavior of the system being modeled, and thus offers machinery that enables us to take this asymmetry into account.

4.3. *Ontology*

We define the following key concepts that form the basis of our approach:

- **Individual Behavior** ($u \in U$): Individual actors make their own choices based on factors that are not known or knowable to system modelers or designers. These choices influence the evolution of the organization but are not strictly determined by any external control.

- **Pattern of Behavior** ($g : X \rightarrow U$): A representation of *observed patterns* in individual actions as state-dependent policies. This captures how individual behavior tends to correlate with specific states of the organization.
- **Situation** ($x \in X$): The *state of the organization* at a given time. Actors take their concrete choices with **partial awareness** of the system's state and dynamics. They have beliefs but not full knowledge of the consequences of their actions.
- **Dynamics** ($f : X \times U \rightarrow X$): A representation of how the organization's *state evolves* as a result of the actions taken by individuals. It models the transition process from one situation to another.
- **Protocol** ($U_x \subset U$): A set of *humanly constructed rules, norms, or shared strategies* that specify a subset of actions available to individuals in a given situation, thereby coordinating individual behavior.
- **Property** ($V : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$): A function that can be understood as a *loss function encoding a pattern* in the system's state. It provides a measure of how well the system aligns with some desired or undesired behavior.
- **Institution** ($\Delta V(x) \leq 0$): An *enduring pattern of behavior* where $V(x)$ remains stable (in the sense of Lyapunov) over time, indicating that the system maintains certain properties despite variations in specific situations and individual actions.

4.4. *Implications of this Approach*

The precise innovation of GDS is the observation that, mathematically speaking, it is not necessary to assert a control law $g(x)$ to produce a desirable property—it suffices to introduce a protocol that limits actions *just enough* to ensure the property of interest. It is worth noting that although institutional economists often identify patterns in $g(x)$ as institutions, we can use $V(x)$ without loss of generality simply by defining $V(x)$ as a loss function expressing the deviation of the $V(x_t) = \|u_t - u_t^*\|^2$ where u_t is the observed behavior and $u_t^* = g(x_t)$, the expected behavior.

The benefit of building on the control engineering literature to develop this approach is that doing so gives us the composing and nesting properties of control systems practically for free. For general results, see Jan C. Willems's "The Behavioral Approach to Open and Interconnected Systems."³² For a GDS-specific discussion of composability, "Block Diagrams for Categorical Cybernetics."³³

While this method provides a clear path for the analysis of institutions as persistent patterns in the behavior exhibited by organizations, and for the design of protocols via control-theoretic methods in order to modify or stabilize those institutions, it also invites important questions regarding the degrees of restriction to be tolerated, relative to the benefits of the desired stable properties.

As shown in “A State-Space Modeling Framework for Engineering Blockchain-Enabled Economic Systems,”³⁰ users of the Bitcoin Network tolerate the restriction “no double-spends” to induce the global property of a stable total supply of 21 million Bitcoin. Cryptographically-secured software systems, however, are significantly more susceptible to this type of formal analysis than organizations where the *rules in use* may deviate significantly from the *rules in form*.³⁴

Furthermore, some of our most important institutions emerge from organizations in which the choices actors make with their degrees of freedom contribute meaningfully to the institution. Markets, for example, do not exist to *set* prices; they clear transactions and *discover* prices. In “Economic Games as Estimators,” Zargham *et al.* show that a particular set of protocols implemented in automated market makers have the property of being “price estimators”; the price estimate is realized when individual actors exercise their freedoms within the protocol.³⁵ In the kidney exchange example from Roth, the key properties are fairness and efficiency, but there is no notion of price.²³

In practice, organizations are heterogeneous and distributed — entangled with each other such that we, as modelers, must make choices about what is in and out of scope. Modeling involves subjective decisions, such as how to divide stakeholders into groups with similar action-situations as well as similar incentives and preferences.^d Continuing with our control engineering approach, suppose the actors are denoted $i \in S$ and that each actor has a set of observables $y_i \in Y_i$ and controllables $u_i \in U_i$, representing what they *can see* and what they *can do* respectively. The realized behavior at any time is the Cartesian product of all the individual actor behavior $U = \bigotimes_{i \in S} U_i$, as informed by their observables and constrained by their

^dWhile the use of advanced modeling techniques can sometimes be viewed as problematic for questions in political science, we appeal to Primo and Clark’s “A Model Discipline” for the argument that models are an integral part of political science.³⁶ Keeping with an engineering ethos, we strive to use models as tools in service to the public, rather than as a means of manipulation. Our engineering-informed approach to modeling is documented in “Method for Functional Decomposition of Organizations and Their Environments.”³⁷

respective controllables. This consideration attends to North’s insistence on the separation of the actors from the rules of the game; it also provides the basis for the dynamics to be distributed across local action situations k , such that $f(x, u) = [\dots, f_k(x, u), \dots]$ to be set up in a manner that represents complex and varied local actuation-situations, including topologies with non-trivial power disparities between actor groups. The topology of the network can take on arbitrary causal patterns such as those described in Multi-Agent Influence Diagrams (MAIDs).³⁸ Furthermore, modeling overlapping action-situations within such a representation $f(x, u)$ provides a more formal perspective on what Vincent and Elinor Ostrom’s work refers to as *polycentricity*^{39,40} — if we also introduce a plethora of distinct $V_j(x)$ representing a range of dynamically entangled properties, consistent with North’s “institutional matrix” and with Abigail Devereaux’s work in “Multiple Games Analysis: A Petri Dish for Growing Polycentric Orders.”⁴¹

Equipped with these additional concepts, we can turn our attention to developing models of organizations that enable us to explore the impact of potential protocols on those organizations’ system-level behaviors. Leaping directly to modeling, however, would be akin to building a house without blueprints or a stable foundation; instead, a rigorous and responsible engineering process must begin by surveying the field and mapping the critical loci at which meaningful interventions might be designed.

5. Conclusion

Rehabilitating society’s institutions is not just about fixing what is broken — it is about designing for a future where stability, variety, and adaptability co-exist. Historically, organizations have been controlled through document-based policy paradigms, where governance relied on formalized rules, laws, and regulations.⁴² Today, we are witnessing a shift toward a data-driven, software-mediated protocol paradigm, where intra- and inter-organizational processes are increasingly embedded in digital systems, algorithms, and automated governance mechanisms.⁴³ This transformation offers both opportunities and risks, as it reconfigures how institutions stabilize behavior while allowing for adaptive evolution.

“Science,” for example, can be understood as a distributed organization whose system-level behavior of producing and disseminating reliable shared knowledge is stabilized by that organization’s defining protocol: the Scientific Method. Science has entered the digital era in an *ad hoc* manner, leaning heavily on digital publishers, citation metrics, and algorithmic

evaluation measures that have arguably destabilized, rather than reinforced, its core epistemic properties. Promising endeavors such as NumFOCUS’s “OpenSource Science Initiative” and decentralized scientific infrastructures like the DeSci Network, however, suggest that a more deliberate and constructive transition is possible.^{44,45}

The distributed organization “engineering” is similarly characterized by *its* defining protocol, the Engineering Design Process, which stabilizes the system-level behavior of transforming knowledge into practical, safe, and reliable systems that meet human needs. Engineering has confronted the challenges of digital transformation with model-based systems engineering (MBSE), successfully integrating system design into digital workflows, executable models, and dynamic document generation.^{46,47} Meanwhile, open-source software communities are pioneering governance mechanisms using git protocol-based coordination tools. These approaches offer compelling templates for protocol-driven institutional design — where modularity, version control, and transparency can enhance institutional resilience.

At the frontiers of institutional design, we find work that challenges us to think beyond the constraints of legacy governance models. Kei Kreutler’s exploration of designing for unprecedented situations urges us to engineer institutions that can function in radically novel environments.⁴⁸ Ellie Rennie’s ethnographic study of SourceCred introduces the concept of “terraforming” organizations, and shows how new protocols can reconstitute economic landscapes and redefine value coordination.⁴⁹ Rennie and Potts extend this line of inquiry with their theory of contribution goods, where value is dictated by protocols of production and exchange, rather than traditional market pricing.⁷ In a similar vein, Austin Wade Smith conceptualizes ecological institutions, whose explicit function is to stabilize the fragile and visibly unhealthy (and unstable) relationship between human society and ecological systems.⁵⁰

These emerging frameworks suggest that protocolization provides a unifying lens for institutional design. By decomposing institutions into their constituent protocols, we can pinpoint failure points, reinforce stability, and enhance adaptability in a modular, recursive fashion. This shift from monolithic structures to dynamic, reconfigurable systems enables organizations to respond to complex challenges like climate change, public health crises, and the digitization of civic engagement — without becoming brittle or obsolete.

We began this chapter by reviewing literature from institutional economics, cybernetics, and other related fields. We then presented a control-

theoretic approach to institutional design that focuses on stabilizing desirable properties via the introduction of protocols. Finally, we extrapolated the digitalization trend to hypothesize that a control-theoretic approach to designing and governing institutions via protocols is not only possible but necessary, given the complexity of our society and the severity of its issues.

In the end, we believe our conception of institutions enables a more rigorous approach to their design, and opens up new possibilities for their renovation. We have found that top-down control and rigid rules are not required in order to implement organizations that can withstand shocks while supporting diverse forms of local and regional action; the urgent (but achievable) work of re-stabilizing our institutions can be accomplished with *protocols*. By aligning organizations with their intended purposes while embedding adaptability at their core, we can lay the groundwork for a society that is resilient, cooperative, and capable of thriving amid uncertainty.

References

1. D. C. North, *Institutions, Institutional Change and Economic Performance*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK (1990).
2. E. Ostrom, *Governing the Commons: The Evolution of Institutions for Collective Action*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK (1990).
3. S. E. S. Crawford and E. Ostrom, A grammar of institutions, *American Political Science Review*. **89**(3), 582–600 (1995).
4. G. M. Hodgson, What are institutions?, *Journal of Economic Issues*. **40**(1), 1–25 (2006). doi: 10.1080/00213624.2006.11506879.
5. S. Beer, *Designing Freedom*. John Wiley & Sons, London (1974).
6. S. Beer, What is cybernetics?, *Kybernetes*. **31**(2), 209–219 (2002). doi: 10.1108/03684920210417283.
7. H. K. Khalil, *Nonlinear Systems*, 3rd edn. Prentice Hall (2001). ISBN 0-13-067389-7.
8. E. D. Sontag, *Mathematical Control Theory: Deterministic Finite Dimensional Systems*, 2nd edn. Springer (1999). ISBN 0-387-98489-5. URL <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-1-4757-3048-7>.
9. G. Beuster, O. Leistert, and T. Röhle, Protocol, *Internet Policy Review*. **11**(1) (2022). doi: 10.14763/2022.1.1651. URL <https://doi.org/10.14763/2022.1.1651>.
10. N. A. Lynch, *Distributed Algorithms*. Morgan Kaufmann, San Francisco (1996).
11. A. R. Galloway, *Protocol: How Control Exists After Decentralization*. MIT Press, Cambridge, MA (2004).
12. S. S. Kia, B. Van Scoy, J. Cortes, R. A. Freeman, K. M. Lynch, and S. Martinez, Tutorial on dynamic average consensus: The problem, its applications,

- and the algorithms, *IEEE Control Systems Magazine*. **39**(3), 40–72 (2019). doi: 10.1109/MCS.2019.2900783.
13. H. Uchiyama, H. Ishii, and K. Sakurama, *Emergent Behavior Detection and Task Coordination for Multiagent Systems*. Springer (2022). ISBN 978-3-030-86895-6. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-86896-3. URL <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-030-86896-3>.
 14. J. S. Shamma, ed., *Cooperative Control of Multi-Agent Systems: A Consensus Region Approach*. Automation and Control Engineering, Springer, New York (2007). ISBN 978-0-387-69171-0. doi: 10.1007/978-0-387-69171-0.
 15. N. Wiener, *Cybernetics: Or Control and Communication in the Animal and the Machine*. MIT Press, Cambridge, MA (1949).
 16. R. Axelrod, *The Evolution of Cooperation*. Basic Books, New York, NY (1984). ISBN 9780465021215. URL <https://www.basicbooks.com/titles/robert-axelrod/the-evolution-of-cooperation/9780465005642/>.
 17. W. H. Sandholm, *Population Games and Evolutionary Dynamics*. MIT Press, Cambridge, MA (2010). ISBN 9780262195874. URL <https://mitpress.mit.edu/9780262195874/population-games-and-evolutionary-dynamics/>.
 18. D. Acemoglu and J. A. Robinson, *Why Nations Fail: The Origins of Power, Prosperity, and Poverty*. Crown Business, New York (2012).
 19. M. Zargham, J. Zartler, K. Nabben, R. Goldberg, and J. Emmett, Disambiguating autonomy, *Zenodo* (2023). doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8239311. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8239311>.
 20. T. Swann, *Anarchist Cybernetics: Control and Communication in Radical Politics*. Bristol University Press (2020). ISBN 978-1-5292-0879-5. URL <https://bristoluniversitypress.co.uk/anarchist-cybernetics>.
 21. S. Voshmgir and M. Zargham, Foundations of cryptoeconomic systems, *Research Institute for Cryptoeconomics Working Paper Series* (2020).
 22. A. E. Roth, The economist as engineer: Game theory, experimentation, and computation as tools for design economics, *Econometrica*. **70**(4), 1341–1378 (2002). doi: 10.1111/1468-0262.00335. URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/1468-0262.00335>.
 23. A. E. Roth, T. Sönmez, and M. U. Ünver, Kidney exchange, *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*. **119**(2), 457–488 (2004). doi: 10.1162/0033553041382157.
 24. J.-C. Rochet and J. Tirole, Platform competition in two-sided markets, *Journal of the European Economic Association*. **1**(4), 990–1029 (2003). doi: 10.1162/154247603322493212. URL <https://academic.oup.com/jeea/article/1/4/990/2280902>.
 25. N. Srnicek, *Platform Capitalism*. Polity Press (2017). ISBN 978-1-5095-0486-2. URL <https://www.politybooks.com/bookdetail/?isbn=9781509504862>.
 26. J. Shorish. Market design lessons for 'safety first' institutional engineering. <https://blog.block.science/market-design-lessons-for-safety-first-institutional-engineering/> (2023). Accessed: 2025-01-29.
 27. I. V. Chremos and A. A. Malikopoulos, Mechanism design theory in con-

- trol engineering: A tutorial and overview of applications in communication, power grid, transportation, and security systems, *IEEE Control Systems Magazine*. **44**(1), 57–78 (2024). doi: 10.1109/MCS.2023.3329919. URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10384599/>.
28. E. Alston, Governance as conflict: Constitution of shared values defining future margins of disagreement, *MIT Computational Law Report* (dec 5, 2022). <https://law.mit.edu/pub/governanceasconflict>.
 29. M. Zargham and K. Nabben, Aligning ‘decentralized autonomous organization’ to precedents in cybernetics, *MIT Computational Law Report* (nov 20, 2023). <https://law.mit.edu/pub/dao-precedents-cybernetics>.
 30. M. Zargham, Z. Zhang, and V. Preciado, A state-space modeling framework for engineering blockchain-enabled economic systems, *arXiv preprint* (2018). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/1807.00955>.
 31. M. Zargham and J. Shorish, Generalized dynamical systems: Foundations, *WU Vienna University of Economics and Business. Working Paper Series* (2022). Pre-publication working paper.
 32. J. C. Willems, The behavioral approach to open and interconnected systems, *IEEE Control Systems Magazine*. **27**(6), 46–99 (2007). doi: 10.1109/MCS.2007.906923.
 33. M. Zargham and J. Shorish, Block diagrams for categorical cybernetics, *Available at SSRN 4569037* (2023).
 34. E. Ostrom, R. Gardner, and J. Walker, *Rules, Games, and Common-Pool Resources*. University of Michigan Press, Ann Arbor (1994). ISBN 978-0472065462. doi: 10.3998/mpub.9739.
 35. M. Zargham, K. Paruch, and J. Shorish. Economic games as estimators. In eds. P. Pardalos, I. Kotsireas, Y. Guo, and W. Knottenbelt, *Mathematical Research for Blockchain Economy*, pp. 125–142, Springer International Publishing, Cham (2020). ISBN 978-3-030-53356-4.
 36. D. M. Primo and K. M. Clarke, *A Model Discipline: Political Science and the Logic of Representations*. Oxford University Press, New York, NY (2012). ISBN 9780195382204. URL <https://global.oup.com/academic/product/a-model-discipline-9780195382204>.
 37. M. Zargham and I. Ben-Meir, Method for functional decomposition of organizations and their environments, *SSRN Electronic Journal* (2023). doi: 10.2139/ssrn.4606672. URL https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4606672.
 38. D. Koller and B. Milch, Multi-agent influence diagrams for representing and solving games, *Games and economic behavior*. **45**(1), 181–221 (2003).
 39. V. Ostrom, C. M. Tiebout, and R. Warren, The organization of government in metropolitan areas: A theoretical inquiry, *American Political Science Review*. **55**(4), 831–842 (1961). doi: 10.2307/1952530. URL <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1952530>.
 40. E. Ostrom, Beyond markets and states: Polycentric governance of complex economic systems, *American Economic Review*. **100**(3), 641–672 (2010). doi: 10.1257/aer.100.3.641. URL <https://www.aeaweb.org/articles?id=10.1257/aer.100.3.641>.

41. A. Devereaux, Multiple games analysis: A petri dish for growing polycentric orders, *SSRN Electronic Journal* (2019). doi: 10.2139/ssrn.3477461. URL https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3477461.
42. R. W. Stone, *Controlling Institutions: International Organizations and the Global Economy*. Cambridge University Press, New York, NY (2011). ISBN 978-0521183062. URL <https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/controlling-institutions/AB18F080C5212E9D145223144E286EA5>.
43. M. Zargham and K. Nabben. Algorithms as policy. URL <https://zenodo.org/record/8283145> (2023). Preprint.
44. NumFOCUS. Open source science initiative (ossoci). URL <https://numfocus.org/open-source-science-initiative-ossoci> Accessed: 2025-01-29.
45. M. Zargham, D. Sisson, C. Vandevoorde, and I. Ben-Meir. Digital public infrastructure for decentralized science. Technical report, DeSci Labs (September, 2024). URL https://nodes.desci.com/dpid/275/v4/root/DeSci_Labs_Report__9_27_24.pdf.
46. R. Karban, F. G. Dekens, S. Herzig, M. Elaasar, and N. Jankevičius. Creating system engineering products with executable models in a model-based engineering environment. In eds. G. Z. Angeli and P. Dierickx, *Modeling, Systems Engineering, and Project Management for Astronomy VII*, vol. 9911, p. 99110B, SPIE (2016). doi: 10.1117/12.2232785. URL <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2232785>.
47. C. Delp, D. Lam, E. Fosse, and C.-Y. Lee. Model based document and report generation for systems engineering. In *2013 IEEE Aerospace Conference*, pp. 1–11 (2013). doi: 10.1109/AERO.2013.6496926.
48. K. Kreutler, How to design a space station, *Journal of Institutional Design* (2024).
49. E. Rennie, The credsperiment: An ethnography of institutional design, *Digital Culture & Society* (2024).
50. A. W. Smith, Ecological institutions: Designing for environmental stability, *Environmental Governance* (2024).